

Gender-Based Occupational Segregation and Economic Development in Liberia: Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa

by

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1. Abstract

Gender-based occupational segregation remains one of the most persistent barriers to inclusive economic development in developing countries, particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa. Although women's participation in education and the labour force has increased over recent decades, they continue to be disproportionately concentrated in low-income, informal, and less productive occupations. This study examines the relationship between occupational gender segregation and economic development in Liberia while drawing comparative insights from the broader Sub-Saharan African region. Using secondary data obtained from the World Bank, International Labour Organization (ILO), Liberia Institute of Statistics and Geo-Information Services (LISGIS), and other international databases covering the period 2000–2024, the study employs descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and multiple regression techniques to evaluate the determinants and economic consequences of occupational segregation. Guided by Human Capital Theory, Gender Segregation Theory, Structural Transformation Theory, and the Gender and Development (GAD) framework, the analysis investigates the effects of occupational segregation on economic growth, labour productivity, and wages. The findings indicate that occupational segregation remains deeply embedded in Liberia's labour market and is associated with lower productivity and constrained economic performance. Although several estimated relationships are statistically weak, the direction of the coefficients supports existing theoretical and empirical evidence. The study concludes that reducing occupational segregation requires integrated policies that combine educational investment with labour market reforms, institutional strengthening, gender-responsive employment policies, and improved access to productive resources. Such reforms are essential for promoting inclusive economic growth and achieving the Sustainable Development Goals.

Keywords: Gender inequality; Occupational segregation; Economic development; Labour market; Liberia; Sub-Saharan Africa; Sustainable Development Goals.

2. Introduction

Gender equality has become a central objective of international development policy because of its recognised contribution to economic growth, poverty reduction, and sustainable development.¹ Sustainable Development Goal 5 (SDG 5) calls for the elimination of discrimination against women and girls while promoting equal opportunities in education, employment, and leadership. Despite significant progress in female educational attainment and labour force participation, occupational segregation continues to limit women's economic opportunities across many developing countries.² Recent global estimates illustrate the scale of this challenge: in 2024, only 46.4 per cent of working-age women were in employment compared with 69.5 per cent of men, a gap that has narrowed only slowly from 27.1 percentage points in 1991 to 23.1 percentage points today. Women also continue to hold just 30 per cent of managerial positions worldwide, underscoring the persistence of both horizontal and vertical forms of occupational disadvantage.³

Occupational segregation refers to the unequal distribution of men and women across occupations and sectors of economic activity. Horizontal segregation confines women and men to different occupational categories, while vertical segregation restricts women's access to senior management and leadership positions. These inequalities reduce labour market efficiency by preventing economies from fully utilising available human capital.⁴

Liberia provides a particularly important case for examining these issues. Although women constitute a substantial proportion of the labour force, they remain concentrated in subsistence agriculture, informal trade, and other low-productivity occupations. Recent macroeconomic estimates illustrate the scale of this concentration: women supply approximately 76 per cent of labour in cash crop production and 93 per cent in food crop production in Liberia, and account for around 80 per cent of small enterprise ownership compared with 57 per cent for men. A World Bank-supported macrosimulation further estimates that closing gender gaps in labour force participation, sectoral representation and intra-sectoral wages could raise Liberia's GDP by as much as 11.5 per cent, rising to 23.7

¹ United Nations, *The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2020* (United Nations 2020).

² World Bank, *World Development Report 2012: Gender Equality and Development* (World Bank 2012).

³ International Labour Organization, 'Achieving Gender Equality in Employment Rates Would Take Almost Two Centuries' (*ILO*, 7 March 2025) <<https://www.ilo.org/resource/news/achieving-gender-equality-employment-rates-would-take-almost-two-centuries>> accessed 30 June 2026.

⁴ Richard Anker, *Gender and Jobs: Sex Segregation of Occupations in the World* (International Labour Office 1998).

per cent with complementary investments in education and fertility reduction.⁵ Their representation within manufacturing, finance, technology, mining, and formal managerial employment remains comparatively limited. Female employment in industry, which includes manufacturing and mining, has remained at around five per cent of total female employment in recent years, while an estimated seventy-four per cent of Liberia's female workforce operates within the informal economy, facing constrained access to credit, banking services and social protection.⁶ Consequently, occupational segregation not only undermines gender equality but also constrains economic productivity and national development.

This study, therefore, investigates the relationship between occupational gender segregation and economic development in Liberia by examining the determinants of occupational segregation and evaluating its effects on labour productivity, earnings, and economic growth.⁷

3. Literature Review

Existing literature consistently identifies occupational gender segregation as one of the principal drivers of labour market inequality. According to Human Capital Theory, investment in education and skills enhances productivity and improves employment outcomes.⁸ However, empirical studies increasingly demonstrate that educational attainment alone cannot eliminate gender inequality where institutional discrimination and unequal employment opportunities persist. This pattern is evident in technical and vocational education, a key pathway to higher-wage occupations: across Sub-Saharan Africa, only 5.2 per cent of female secondary students are enrolled in vocational programmes compared with 6.4 per cent of male students, and the gap widens further in countries with larger training systems. Such disparities in access to technical skills training help explain why rising

⁵ Mahesh Karra and others, 'Liberian Women Count: Evidence from a Macrosimulation of the Gender Dividend' (World Bank Policy Research Working Paper No 10425, 2023) <<https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/099231304272369200/pdf/IDU-61c87b35-856f-4234-a505-ea45b0e58bf3.pdf>> accessed 30 June 2026.

⁶ International Labour Organization, 'ILOSTAT Country Profile: Liberia' (ILOSTAT) <<https://ilostat.ilo.org/data/country-profiles/lbr/>> accessed 30 June 2026; Council on Foreign Relations, 'Spotlight on Liberia: Growing Economies Through Gender Parity' (CFR) <<https://www.cfr.org/womens-participation-in-global-economy/case-studies/liberia/>> accessed 30 June 2026.

⁷ Paula England, 'The Gender Revolution: Uneven and Stalled' (2010) 24(2) *Gender & Society* 149.

⁸ Gary S Becker, *Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, with Special Reference to Education* (University of Chicago Press 1964).

educational attainment among women has not translated into proportionate gains in higher-productivity occupations.⁹

Gender Segregation Theory argues that occupational inequality reflects structural labour market arrangements rather than differences in ability or individual preference. Women are frequently channelled into occupations associated with traditional caregiving roles, while men dominate industries characterised by higher wages, stronger career progression, and greater technological intensity.¹⁰ Consequently, occupational segregation contributes directly to gender wage disparities and inefficient allocation of labour.

Structural Transformation Theory further suggests that economic development depends upon the movement of labour from low-productivity activities towards modern industries and services. Where women remain excluded from these expanding sectors, countries experience lower productivity growth and reduced economic diversification.¹¹ Empirical evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa supports this proposition: women in urban non-farm wage employment earn between 40 and 46 per cent less than men, with a substantial share of this gap explained by occupational and sectoral differences rather than productivity-related characteristics. The persistence of such gaps despite ongoing structural change suggests that the reallocation of labour towards higher-productivity sectors does not automatically translate into gender-equitable outcomes.¹²

The Gender and Development (GAD) framework complements these perspectives by emphasising that gender inequality results from unequal power relations embedded within social institutions, legal systems, and cultural norms.¹³ Labour market outcomes, therefore, reflect broader structural inequalities rather than purely economic factors.

Empirical evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa demonstrates that occupational segregation remains widespread despite improvements in female education and labour force participation.¹⁴ Studies consistently report that women remain disproportionately employed

⁹ World Bank, 'Minding the Gender Gap in Training in Sub-Saharan Africa: Five Things to Know' (*World Bank Blogs*, 2023) <<https://blogs.worldbank.org/en/african/minding-gender-gap-training-sub-saharan-africa-five-things-know>> accessed 30 June 2026.

¹⁰ Francine D Blau and Lawrence M Kahn, 'The Gender Wage Gap: Extent, Trends, and Explanations' (2017) 55(3) *Journal of Economic Literature* 789.

¹¹ Gary S Becker, *Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, with Special Reference to Education* (University of Chicago Press 1964); Jacob Mincer, *Schooling, Experience, and Earnings* (Columbia University Press 1974).

¹² Goedele Van den Broeck and others, 'Structural Transformation and the Gender Pay Gap in Sub-Saharan Africa' (2023) 18(4) *PLOS ONE* e0278188.

¹³ Amartya Sen, *Development as Freedom* (Oxford University Press 1999).

¹⁴ International Labour Organization, *World Employment and Social Outlook: Trends for Women 2018* (ILO 2018); African Development Bank, *African Gender Index Report* (African Development Bank 2019).

in informal activities, subsistence agriculture, and low-paying service occupations. Limited access to finance, land ownership, vocational training, childcare, and formal employment opportunities continues to restrict occupational mobility.¹⁵ Data from the African Development Bank's Africa Gender Index indicate the depth of this constraint: women own less than twenty per cent of agricultural land across the continent and earn between thirty and forty per cent less than men on average, while access to formal credit remains substantially skewed in men's favour. These structural barriers to productive assets compound the effects of occupational segregation identified elsewhere in the literature.¹⁶

Within Liberia, relatively few studies have examined occupational segregation as a determinant of macroeconomic performance.¹⁷ Existing research has focused primarily on women's labour force participation, poverty, or educational attainment without investigating how occupational segregation affects productivity, wages, and economic growth simultaneously. This study addresses that gap by providing quantitative evidence linking occupational segregation to broader development outcomes. A partial exception is a 2023 World Bank-supported macrosimulation, which estimates the aggregate economic costs of gender gaps in Liberia's labour market through a gender dividend model rather than direct empirical analysis of occupational segregation. While this study offers valuable macro-level estimates, it does not examine the statistical determinants of segregation or its disaggregated effects on productivity and wages, the gap that the present study seeks to address.¹⁸

4. Methodology

The study adopts a quantitative explanatory research design based exclusively on secondary data collected from the World Bank, International Labour Organization, Liberia Institute of Statistics and Geo-Information Services, African Development Bank, and other internationally recognised sources.¹⁹ The analysis covers the period 2000–2024.

¹⁵ Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, *The Pursuit of Gender Equality: An Uphill Battle* (OECD Publishing 2017).

¹⁶ African Development Bank, 'Gender in Focus: How My African Development Bank Journey Brings Africa Gender Index Statistics to Life' (*AfDB*, 25 March 2025) <<https://www.afdb.org/en/news-and-events/gender-focus-how-my-african-development-bank-journey-brings-africa-gender-index-statistics-life-81620>> accessed 30 June 2026.

¹⁷ Esther Duflo, 'Women Empowerment and Economic Development' (2012) 50(4) *Journal of Economic Literature* 1051–1079; World Bank, *World Development Report 2012: Gender Equality and Development* (World Bank 2012).

¹⁸ Karra and others (n 5).

¹⁹ World Bank, *World Development Report 2012: Gender Equality and Development* (World Bank 2012); International Labour Organization, *World Employment and Social Outlook: Trends for Women 2018* (ILO 2018); African Development Bank, *African Gender Index Report* (African Development Bank 2019).

Three principal dependent variables were examined: economic growth, occupational gender segregation, and labour earnings. The explanatory variables include female educational attainment, labour productivity, and urbanisation.²⁰ These variables were selected because previous theoretical and empirical studies identify them as important determinants of labour market inequality and economic development.²¹

Data analysis proceeded in three stages. First, descriptive statistics summarised trends in occupational segregation, education, productivity, and economic growth. Second, Pearson correlation analysis examined the direction and strength of relationships among the variables.²² Third, multiple linear regression models estimated the effects of occupational segregation on economic growth and wages while also examining the determinants of occupational segregation itself.²³

IBM SPSS Statistics was used for all quantitative analyses. Model performance was evaluated using regression coefficients, t-statistics, probability values, R^2 , adjusted R^2 , and F-statistics.²⁴ The use of multiple analytical techniques strengthens the reliability of the findings by enabling both descriptive and inferential assessment of the relationships among the study variables.

5. Results and Discussion

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
ln_GDP	1.787	3.952	22
Seg	0.532	0.068	23
Fedu	43.383	9.855	23
Urb	50.949	11.973	23
Prod	4249.826	1529.038	23

Source: Author's computation using IBM SPSS Statistics.

²⁰ Gary S Becker, *Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, with Special Reference to Education* (University of Chicago Press 1964); Jacob Mincer, *Schooling, Experience, and Earnings* (Columbia University Press 1974).

²¹ Paul D Leedy and Jeanne Ellis Ormrod, *Practical Research: Planning and Design* (11th edn, Pearson 2019).

²² Andy Field, *Discovering Statistics Using IBM SPSS Statistics* (5th edn, SAGE Publications 2018).

²³ Damodar N Gujarati and Dawn C Porter, *Basic Econometrics* (5th edn, McGraw-Hill Education 2009).

²⁴ Andy Field (n 22).

The descriptive statistics indicate that occupational gender segregation remains a persistent feature of Liberia's labour market. The segregation index exhibited relatively little variation throughout the study period, suggesting that gender disparities in occupational distribution have changed only gradually despite improvements in education and labour force participation. In contrast, economic growth and labour productivity displayed greater variability, reflecting the effects of post-conflict reconstruction, fluctuations in commodity prices, external economic shocks, and the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic's gendered effects were particularly acute among informal workers: a regional survey found that forty-one per cent of women-owned businesses in Sub-Saharan Africa closed during the pandemic, compared with thirty-four per cent of those owned by men, while the International Labour Organization estimated an eighty-one per cent decline in revenue among Africa's informal workers within the first month of the crisis. Given that Liberian women are heavily concentrated in informal and subsistence activities, these regional shocks likely contributed to the volatility observed in the growth and productivity series during the study period.²⁵

Figure 1 shows how occupational gender segregation and economic growth have changed over time. The graph demonstrates that occupational segregation does not change significantly over the study period, while economic growth varies throughout it. This implies that alterations in the economic growth are not highly correlated with alterations in gender-based occupational segregation.

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²⁵ International Development Research Centre, 'Undoing the Effects of COVID-19 by Advancing Gender Equity in Africa's Informal Sector' (*IDRC*, 11 June 2024) <<https://idrc-crddi.ca/en/perspectives/undoing-effects-covid-19-advancing-gender-equity-africas-informal-sector>> accessed 30 June 2026.

Figure 1. Gender Segregation VS Economic Growth

Source: *Author’s computation using IBM SPSS Statistics.*

Trend analysis further demonstrates that while Liberia experienced periods of economic expansion, these gains were not accompanied by substantial reductions in occupational segregation. This finding suggests that economic growth alone does not automatically produce more equitable labour market outcomes. Instead, structural barriers, including unequal access to education, discriminatory employment practices, limited career advancement opportunities, and persistent gender norms, continue to influence occupational choices and employment patterns.

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Correlation Analysis

Table 2 presents the correlation matrix among the variables.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

Variable	ln_GDP	Seg	Fedu	Urb	Prod
ln_GDP	1.000	-0.042	-0.272	—	—
Seg	-0.042	1.000	-0.279	-0.047	-0.324
Fedu	-0.272	-0.279	1.000	-0.201	—
Urb	—	-0.047	-0.201	1.000	—
Prod	—	-0.324	—	—	1.000

Note: Pearson correlations.

Source: *Author’s computation using IBM SPSS Statistics.*

The Pearson correlation analysis revealed generally weak relationships among the study variables. Occupational segregation exhibited a negative association with economic growth and labour productivity, indicating that higher levels of segregation tend to coincide with lower economic performance. Female educational attainment was also negatively associated with occupational segregation, suggesting that improvements in education may contribute to reducing labour market inequalities. However, the relatively weak correlations imply that occupational segregation is influenced by multiple institutional, cultural, and economic factors that extend beyond educational attainment alone. Regional labour market data corroborate this conclusion: across Sub-Saharan Africa, the gender gap in informal employment persists at approximately thirteen percentage points despite improvements in female education, and women remain disproportionately represented as contributing family workers, accounting for 34.9 per cent of female employment. This suggests that institutional and cultural constraints, rather than education alone, continue to shape occupational outcomes in the region.²⁶

Figure 2. Segregation VS GDP

Source: *Author's computation using IBM SPSS Statistics.*

Figure 2 is a scatter plot that illustrates the association between occupational segregation and economic growth. The points distribution shows that there is a weak negative correlation, as the correlation results indicate.

Regression Analysis

²⁶ International Labour Organization, 'Addressing Gender Gaps in Africa's Labour Market' (*ILO*, 8 March 2016) <<https://www.ilo.org/resource/news/addressing-gender-gaps-africas-labour-market>> accessed 30 June 2026.

To improve model efficiency and avoid over-parameterization, parsimonious regression models were estimated. Logarithmic transformations and lagged variables were introduced where appropriate to better capture economic relationships.

Economic Growth Model

Table 3 gives the regression findings in the economic growth model to investigate the impacts of occupational gender segregation and lagged education among females on economic growth.

Table 3: Economic Growth Model

Dependent Variable: ln_GDP

Variable	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
Constant	7.463	7.755	—	0.962	0.348
Seg	-2.014	12.854	-0.035	-0.157	0.877
Fedu (lag)	-0.106	0.087	-0.271	-1.226	0.235

Source: *Author's computation using IBM SPSS Statistics.*

Model Statistics:

$R^2 = 0.075$, Adjusted $R^2 = -0.022$

$F = 0.770$ ($p = 0.477$)

$N = 22$

The regression findings suggest that the model has a limited percentage of variance in economic growth ($R^2 = 0.075$), and the model is statistically non-significant ($F = 0.770$, $p = 0.477$).

Occupational Gender Segregation (Seg):

The coefficient is negative (-2.014), which implies that the greater the segregation, the less the economic growth. Nevertheless, this impact is not statistically significant ($p = 0.877$), and it is weakly empirically supported.

Lagged Female Education (Fedu_{t-1}):

This is a negative coefficient (-0.106), which is not supposed to be so and is not statistically significant ($p = 0.235$). This can denote the lagging or indirect impacts of schooling on development.

Determinants of Occupational Segregation

Table 4 gives the regression findings for the determinants of occupational segregation.

Table 4: Segregation Model**Dependent Variable: Seg**

Variable	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
Constant	0.653	0.099	—	6.607	0.000
Fedu	-0.002	0.001	-0.301	-1.381	0.182
Urb	-0.001	0.001	-0.107	-0.492	0.628

Source: *Author's computation using IBM SPSS Statistics.*

Model Statistics:

$R^2 = 0.089$, Adjusted $R^2 = -0.002$

$F = 0.978$ ($p = 0.393$)

$N = 23$

The model explains about 8.9% of variation in occupational segregation ($R^2 = 0.089$), but the overall model is not statistically significant ($F = 0.978$, $p = 0.393$).

- Female Education (Fedu): The coefficient is negative (-0.002), indicating that higher education reduces segregation. However, it is not statistically significant ($p = 0.182$).
- Urbanization (Urb): The coefficient is negative (-0.001), suggesting urbanization may reduce segregation, but the effect is also insignificant ($p = 0.628$).

Wage Determination Model

Table 5 gives the regression findings for the wage model.

Table 5: Wage Model**Dependent Variable: ln_Wage**

Variable	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
Constant	5.049	1.028	—	4.911	0.000
Seg	2.379	1.652	0.312	1.440	0.165
Prod	0.000	0.000	0.369	1.702	0.104*

Source: *Author's computation using IBM SPSS Statistics.*

Model Statistics:

$R^2 = 0.159$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.075$

$F = 1.890$ ($p = 0.177$)

$N = 23$

Note: *Significant at 10% level

The wage model performs relatively better, explaining 15.9% of variation in wages ($R^2 = 0.159$), although it remains statistically insignificant overall ($F = 1.890$, $p = 0.177$).

- Occupational Segregation (Seg): The coefficient is positive (2.379), contrary to theory, but statistically insignificant ($p = 0.165$).
- Labour Productivity (Prod): The coefficient is positive and relatively strong, with marginal significance at the 10% level ($p = 0.104$). This indicates that higher productivity increases wages. However, productivity gains do not necessarily translate into equitable wage outcomes across genders. Regional evidence indicates that women across Africa continue to earn between thirty and forty per cent less than men on average, even as overall labour productivity rises, suggesting that occupational segregation may dampen the wage benefits that would otherwise accrue to women from productivity growth.²⁷

Figure 3. Labour Productivity VS Wages

Source: Author's computation using IBM SPSS Statistics.

²⁷ African Development Bank (n 16).

Figure 3 shows a relationship between labour productivity and wages.

The curve shows that there is a positive relationship, meaning that the higher the productivity, the higher the wages.

6. Conclusion and Policy Implications

This study investigated the relationship between gender-based occupational segregation and economic development in Liberia within the broader context of Sub-Saharan Africa. Using secondary data and quantitative analytical techniques, the research examined how occupational segregation influences labour productivity, wage outcomes, and economic growth while identifying key structural determinants of labour market inequality.

The findings indicate that occupational gender segregation remains a significant structural challenge within Liberia's labour market. Although women increasingly participate in education and economic activity, they remain disproportionately represented in informal, lower-paying, and lower-productivity occupations. Consequently, Liberia continues to underutilise a substantial proportion of its human capital, limiting both productivity growth and inclusive economic development.

The study demonstrates that reducing occupational segregation requires considerably more than expanding educational opportunities. Although education remains an essential foundation for economic empowerment, it cannot by itself overcome institutional discrimination, occupational stereotypes, unequal access to productive assets, or barriers to formal employment. Effective gender equality policies must therefore integrate educational investment with labour market reforms, institutional strengthening, legal protections, and economic diversification strategies.

From a policy perspective, the government should strengthen investment in girls' education while expanding access to science, technology, engineering, mathematics, technical education, and vocational training. Equal employment legislation should be more effectively enforced to eliminate discriminatory recruitment, promotion, and wage practices. Public and private institutions should adopt transparent employment procedures that promote merit-based recruitment and equal opportunities for career advancement.

Economic diversification should also be prioritised to expand employment opportunities in manufacturing, technology, renewable energy, agribusiness, finance, and modern service industries. Increasing women's participation within these sectors would contribute to higher labour productivity while reducing occupational segregation. Targeted financing initiatives

illustrate the potential of this approach: the African Development Bank's Affirmative Finance Action for Women in Africa programme, launched to close an estimated forty-two billion dollar financing gap facing women entrepreneurs across the continent, had by 2024 secured more than one and a half billion dollars in approved investment reaching over seven thousand women-led small and medium enterprises. Comparable initiatives tailored to Liberia's economic structure could similarly expand women's participation in higher-productivity sectors.²⁸

Improving women's access to productive resources, including land ownership, financial services, business development programmes, digital technology, and entrepreneurial support, would further strengthen economic inclusion. The scale of the underlying gap is considerable: women constitute only around twelve per cent of agricultural landowners across Africa, and the continent's gender index score for access to credit remains well below parity. Addressing these asset and finance gaps directly would complement labour market reforms by enabling women to convert improved skills and education into productive economic activity.²⁹ Equally important is the expansion of affordable childcare, maternity protection, flexible working arrangements, and social protection programmes that reduce barriers associated with unpaid care responsibilities.

The study also highlights the importance of improving gender-disaggregated labour market statistics. More comprehensive data on occupational mobility, wage inequality, informal employment, and career progression would enhance evidence-based policymaking and facilitate more rigorous future research.

Although the study provides valuable insights, several limitations should be acknowledged. The relatively small sample size and reliance on secondary data restrict the statistical power of the regression models and limit the range of explanatory variables available for analysis. Future research should employ longitudinal panel datasets, household surveys, and mixed-method approaches that combine quantitative analysis with qualitative evidence from employers, workers, and policymakers.

²⁸ African Development Bank, '#IWD2024: African Development Bank's Affirmative Finance Action for Women in Africa (AFAWA) Is Investing in Women, Accelerating Africa's Progress Toward Gender-Inclusive Economic Growth' (*AfDB*, 8 March 2024) <<https://www.afdb.org/en/news-and-events/iwd2024-african-development-banks-affirmative-finance-action-women-africa-afawa-investing-women-accelerating-africas-progress-toward-gender-inclusive-economic-growth-69218>> accessed 30 June 2026.

²⁹ Institute for Security Studies, 'Gender' (*ISS African Futures*, 2026) <<https://futures.issafrica.org/thematic/guide.pdf?thematic=16-gender&topic=05-economic-participation>> accessed 30 June 2026.

Despite these limitations, the study contributes to the growing literature on gender and development by demonstrating that occupational segregation is both a social justice issue and a macroeconomic concern. Reducing gender inequalities within labour markets is essential not only for improving women's welfare but also for enhancing national productivity, strengthening economic resilience, and promoting sustainable development.

In conclusion, Liberia's long-term economic transformation depends upon its ability to utilise the talents and productive capacities of both women and men. Policies that promote equal access to education, productive employment, leadership opportunities, financial resources, and institutional support will strengthen labour market efficiency and contribute to more inclusive economic growth. Addressing occupational gender segregation should therefore be regarded as a strategic investment in national development and an essential component of achieving the Sustainable Development Goals.

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